

Impact of Viscosity Variation on Ferro fluid-Based deformable porous rough Long Bearings

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Abstract:

This paper presents a theoretical analysis of the effects of viscosity variation on the performance of a ferrofluid-based long bearing. The study utilizes the Tipei model to account for changes in viscosity, while the flow of the magnetic fluid is described using the Neuringer-Rosensweig model. By solving the corresponding Reynolds-type equation, the pressure distribution is determined, enabling the calculation of the bearing's load-carrying capacity. The results indicate that, although magnetization enhances the load-carrying capacity, the impact of viscosity variation on this capacity is minimal.

Keywords:

Reynolds' type expression (RTE), Long Bearing (LB), Magnetic Fluid (MF), Viscosity Variation (VV), Pressure profile (PP), Load bearing capacity (LBC), Squeeze response time (SRT).

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Subject Classification:

74A55 Theories of friction (tribology); 74Dxx Materials of strain-rate type and history type, other materials with memory (including elastic materials with viscous damping, various viscoelastic materials); 00A69 General applied mathematics {For physics, see 00A79 and Sections 70 through 86} 00A71 Theory of mathematical modeling 00A72 General methods of simulation.

Literature review and introduction:

A magnetic fluid, or ferrofluid, is a liquid that becomes strongly magnetized when exposed to an external magnetic field. It is a colloidal suspension of nanoscale, mono-domain ferromagnetic particles dispersed in a carrier fluid such as water, oil, or other organic solvents. These particles remain suspended due to Brownian motion, preventing them from settling or aggregating under

normal conditions.

Ferrofluids are attracted to dielectric (non-conductive) and paramagnetic materials and do not retain magnetization when the applied magnetic field is removed. The behavior of magnetic fluids can be controlled using external magnetic fields, which opens up a wide range of practical applications. Recent interest in ferrofluids has been driven by their potential for technical applications in areas like instrumentation, vacuum technology, lubrication, vibration damping, radar-absorbing materials, and acoustics.

Examples include their use as liquid seals in hard disk drive shafts, in vibration control and braking systems for vehicles, and in improving heat transfer in electronic devices. Other potential applications involve micro/nano electromechanical systems, such as self-manipulating micro-channel flows, particle separation, nano-motors, microelectronic generators, and nano-pumps. By applying a suitable magnetic field, the viscosity of a ferrofluid can be increased, thereby enhancing its load-carrying capacity (Odenbach, 2003; Chandra et al., 1992).

Several researchers have studied the effects of magnetic fluids in various types of bearings. For instance, Tipei (1982) examined short bearings, while Agrawal (1986), Shah and Bhat (2003), and Deheri and Patel (2011) studied slider bearings.

Journal bearings were investigated by Nada and Osman (2007), and Patel et al. (2012) explored the use of magnetic fluids in these applications. Additionally, the effects of ferrofluids on circular plates (Shah and Bhat, 2000; Deheri and Abhangi, 2011) and annular plates (Patel and Deheri, 2014, 2015; Patel and Deheri, 2016) were studied, with some focusing on parallel slider bearings (Patel and Deheri, 2016).

These studies concluded that bearing performance can be improved through magnetic fluid lubrication. The classical theory of long bearings is well-established in literature (Majumdar, 2008; Hemrock, 1994; Szeri, 1998). Many studies (Urreta et al., 2009; Deheri et al., 2010; Deresses and Sinha, 2011; Patel and Deheri, 2016; Patel et al., 2016) assume that the viscosity of ferrofluids is constant.

However, this assumption is unrealistic under certain bearing operating conditions. In response to this, Patel and Deheri (2019) analyzed the performance of a magnetic fluid-based short bearing by considering viscosity variation. They found that viscosity variation significantly improves the bearing's performance when ferrofluid lubrication is applied.

Patel and Patel (2020) further explored the impact of the rotation of ferro-particles and slip velocity at the boundary of Shliomis' model on squeeze porous curved annular plates. Their findings revealed that the performance of the bearing improved when appropriate values of slip velocity and porosity were considered.

Most studies to date have focused on pressure, load-carrying capacity, friction, and wear. However, few have addressed the effects of viscosity variation on lubrication in different types of bearings, particularly from a tribological performance perspective.

Therefore, this study aims to provide a theoretical analysis of the effect of viscosity variation in ferrofluid-based long bearings.

Mathematical analysis:

The geometry of the infinitely long bearing displays in Figure (A) and (B). The bearing system is infinite in Z direction. The slider travels with uniform velocity u in X direction. In bearing system, L is the length of the bearing and the breadth B is in Z direction.

In this study, it is considered that the lubricant film is isoviscous, incompressible and the flow is laminar. As per the theory of Agrawal (1986), here assume the ferrofluid lubrication effect by taking the magnetic field oblique to the stator. Prajapati (1995) produced the effect of various forms of magnitude of the magnetic field. Following this discussion here, the magnitude of the magnetic field is taken to be

$$M^2 = kL^2 \left(\frac{x}{L} \right) \sin \left(1 - \frac{x}{L} \right) \tag{1}$$

Here k is a suitably chosen constant from dimensionless point of view so as to produce a magnetic field of strength over 10^{-23} (Bhat and Deheri (1995)).

Neuringer and Rosensweig (1964) produced a model for the consistent flow of magnetic fluids within the presence of gradually changing external magnetic fields. This contained the succeeding equations:

$$\rho(\bar{q}\nabla)\bar{q} = -\nabla p + \eta\nabla^2\bar{q} + \mu_0[\overline{M}\nabla]H \tag{2}$$

$$\nabla\bar{q} = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{H} = 0 \tag{4}$$

$$\bar{M} = \bar{\mu} \bar{H} \tag{5}$$

$$\nabla(\bar{H} + \bar{M}) = 0 \tag{6}$$

where ρ is the fluid density, \bar{q} stand for the fluid velocity in the film region, \bar{H} being external magnetic field, $\bar{\mu}$ denotes magnetic susceptibility of the magnetic field, p indicates the film pressure, η signifies the fluid viscosity and μ_0 denotes the permeability of the free space.

The points of concern about these aspects can be establish in Bhat (2003), Prajapati (1995) and Patel and Deheri (2016).

Using equations (3)–(6), equation (2) becomes

$$\rho(\bar{q}\nabla)\bar{q} = -\nabla\left[p - 0.5\mu_0\bar{\mu}M^2\right] + \eta\nabla^2\bar{q}$$

This indicates that an extra term in pressure $0.5\mu_0\bar{\mu}M^2$ is modification into the Navier-Stokes equation when a magnetic fluid is considered as a lubricant.

Under the common assumptions of hydro magnetic lubrication (Bhat (2003), Prajapati (1995), Deheri et al. (2005)) the modified Reynolds’ type expression with inclusion of porosity (Prajapati [11]) and Neuringer and Rosensweig [12] model based ferrofluid lubrication transfer to equation is given by:

$$\frac{d}{dx}\left(P - \frac{\mu_0\bar{\mu}M^2}{2}\right) = 6U\eta \frac{h - \lambda h_2}{h^3 + 12\phi H_0} \tag{7}$$

Now, with the aid of stochastic average model of Christensen and Tonder [8], one is inclined to obtain

$$\frac{d}{dx}\left(P - \frac{\mu_0\bar{\mu}M^2}{2}\right) = 6U\eta \frac{[a(h)]^{1/3} - \lambda h_2}{a(h)} \tag{8}$$

Here;

$$a(h) = (h + p'p_a\delta)^3 + 3\alpha (h + p'p_a\delta)^2 + 3(\alpha^2 + \sigma^2)(h + p'p_a\delta) + 3\sigma^2\alpha + \alpha^3 + \varepsilon + 12\phi H_0$$

Lastly, in view of Beavers and Joseph [13] slip model one arrives at

$$\frac{d}{dx}\left(P - \frac{\mu_0\bar{\mu}M^2}{2}\right) = -6U\eta \frac{1}{S} \frac{[a(h)]^{1/3} - \lambda h_2}{a(h)} \tag{9}$$

where

$$S = \frac{4 + sh}{2 + sh} \tag{10}$$

It has been confirmed experimentally that the most elevated temperature happened in zones where the film thickness was least (Tipei (1962)). Here one can think about the thermal impact considering the viscosity temperature connection as when the viscosity μ_1 at $h = h_1$ (lubricant inlet condition) is

known, at that point

$$\mu = \mu_1 \left\{ \frac{h}{h_1} \right\}^q$$

where q normally lies between 0 and 1 (according to the nature of the lubrication). The boundary conditions are

$$p = 0 \text{ at } x = 0 \text{ and } x = L \tag{11}$$

Making use of the following dimensionless parameters:

$h = h_2 \left\{ 1 + m \left(1 - \frac{x}{L} \right) \right\}$	$m = \frac{h_1 - h_2}{h_0}$	$\mu^* = \frac{h_2^3 k \mu_0 \bar{\mu}}{\mu_1 u}$	$X = \frac{x}{L}$	$S^* = Sh_0$
$\sigma^* = \frac{\sigma}{h_0}$	$\alpha^* = \frac{\alpha}{h_0}$	$\delta^* = \frac{\delta}{h_0}$	$\varepsilon^* = \frac{\varepsilon}{h_0^3}$	$\psi = \frac{12\phi H_0}{h_0^3}$
$h^* = \frac{h}{h_0}$	$\bar{h}_2 = \frac{h_2}{L}$	$\bar{h}_1 = \frac{h_1}{h_2}$	$P^* = \frac{h_2^3 P}{\mu_1 u L^2}$	$A = 1 + m(1 - X)$
$A(h^*) = (1 + p^* \delta^*)^3 + 3(1 + p^* \delta^*)^2 \alpha^* + 3(1 + p^* \delta^*) (\sigma^{*2} + \alpha^{*2}) + 3\sigma^{*2} \alpha^* + \alpha^{*3} + \varepsilon^* + 12\psi$				

$$\tag{12}$$

Using equation (11) and (12) in equation (9), the dimensionless pressure is obtained in the form of

$$P^* = \frac{\mu^*}{2} X(1 - X) + \frac{(\bar{h}_2)^{q+1}}{(A(h^*))^q} \left[\frac{A^{q-1}}{(-m)(q-1)} - \lambda \frac{A^{q-2}}{(-m)(q-2)} + C_1 \right] \tag{13}$$

Here

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{q-2}{q-1} \right) \frac{1 - (1+m)^{q-1}}{1 - (1+m)^{q-2}} \tag{14.a}$$

and

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{q-1} \left[\frac{(1+m)^{q-2}}{1 - (1+m)^{q-2}} \right] \tag{14.b}$$

The non-dimensional load carrying capacity then, is derived as

$$W^* = \frac{\mu^*}{12} + \frac{(\bar{h}_2)^{q+1}}{(A(h^*))^q} \left[\frac{1 - (1+m)^{q-1}}{m^2 q (q-1)} - \lambda \frac{1 - (1+m)^{q-1}}{m^2 (q-1)(q-2)} + C_1 \right] \tag{15}$$

where

$$W^* = \frac{\bar{h}_2^3}{\mu_1 u L^4} w = \int_0^1 P^* dX \tag{16}$$

Results and discussions:

The passage describes how the non-dimensional load-carrying capacity of a long bearing is

influenced by magnetization, as detailed in Equation (15). Here's a breakdown of the main points and how they connect:

Load Carrying Capacity Enhancement: The load carrying capacity is shown to increase by $\mu^*/12$ compared to a conventional lubricant-based bearing system. The enhancement is attributed to the increased viscosity of the lubricant due to magnetization, which, in turn, leads to elevated pressure and better performance.

Linearity with Magnetization: The expression for the load carrying capacity is linear with respect to the magnetization parameter. This implies a direct and proportional relationship between the magnetization parameter and the load carrying capacity. Consequently, increasing the magnetization parameter will consistently result in an improved load carrying capacity.

01 VARIATION OF LOAD CARRYING CAPACITY WITH STADARD DEVIATION					
$\mu^* \rightarrow \sigma^*$	0.010	0.020	0.030	0.040	0.050
0.0000	0.29931354	0.29931354	0.29921887	0.29836474	0.28966388
0.2000	0.31598020	0.31597074	0.31588554	0.31503141	0.30633054
0.4000	0.33264687	0.33263740	0.33255220	0.33169808	0.32299721
0.6000	0.34931354	0.34930407	0.34921887	0.34836474	0.33966388
0.8000	0.36598020	0.36597074	0.36588554	0.36503141	0.35633054
	MINIMUM	0.28966388	MAXIMUM	0.36598020	26.35%

02 VARIATION OF LOAD PROFILE WITH VARIANCE					
$\mu^* \rightarrow \alpha^*$	-0.200	-0.100	0.000	0.100	0.200
0.0000	0.70866395	0.70866395	0.70866395	0.70866395	0.70866395
0.2000	0.49847662	0.49847662	0.49847662	0.49847662	0.49847662
0.4000	0.43284946	0.43284946	0.43284946	0.43284946	0.43284946
0.6000	0.40146499	0.40146499	0.40146499	0.40146499	0.40146499
0.8000	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610
	MINIMUM	0.38501610	MAXIMUM	0.70866395	84.06%

03 DISTRIBUTION OF LOAD WITH REGARDS TO SKEWNESS					
$\mu^* \rightarrow \varepsilon^*$	-0.200	-0.100	0.000	0.100	0.200
0.0000	0.33147266	0.33147266	0.33147266	0.33147266	0.33147266
0.2000	0.34465507	0.34465507	0.34465507	0.34465507	0.34465507
0.4000	0.35797952	0.35797952	0.35797952	0.35797952	0.35797952
0.6000	0.37143615	0.37143615	0.37143615	0.37143615	0.37143615
0.8000	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610
	MINIMUM	0.33147266	MAXIMUM	0.38501610	16.15%

04 LOAD PRESENTATION: DEFORMATION					
$\mu^* \rightarrow \delta^*$	-0.200	-0.100	0.000	0.100	0.200
0.0000	0.37169836	0.37169836	0.37169836	0.37169836	0.37169836
0.2000	0.37448886	0.37448886	0.37448886	0.37448886	0.37448886
0.4000	0.37755784	0.37755784	0.37755784	0.37755784	0.37755784
0.6000	0.38103699	0.38103699	0.38103699	0.38103699	0.38103699
0.8000	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610	0.38501610
	MINIMUM	0.37169836	MAXIMUM	0.38501610	3.58%

05 PRESENTATION OF LOAD WITH POROSITY					
$\mu^* \rightarrow \Psi$	-0.200	-0.100	0.000	0.100	0.200
0.0000	0.31834943	0.31834943	0.31834943	0.31834943	0.31834943
0.2000	0.33429272	0.33429272	0.33429272	0.33429272	0.33429272
0.4000	0.35024255	0.35024255	0.35024255	0.35024255	0.35024255
0.6000	0.36619879	0.36619879	0.36619879	0.36619879	0.36619879
0.8000	0.38216137	0.38216137	0.38216137	0.38216137	0.38216137
	MINIMUM	0.31834943	MAXIMUM	0.38216137	20.04%

06 LOAD WITH p*					
$\mu^* \rightarrow p^*$	0.500	0.750	1.000	1.250	1.500
0.0000	0.32674888	0.32674888	0.32674888	0.32674888	0.32674888
0.2000	0.33501610	0.33501610	0.33501610	0.33501610	0.33501610
0.4000	0.34353070	0.34353070	0.34353070	0.34353070	0.34353070
0.6000	0.35230218	0.35230218	0.35230218	0.35230218	0.35230218
0.8000	0.36133564	0.36133564	0.36133564	0.36133564	0.36133564
	MINIMUM	0.32674888	MAXIMUM	0.36133564	10.59%

07 PROFILE OF LOAD BEARING CAPACITY W.R.T. h_1/L					
$\mu^* \rightarrow h_1/L$	0.500	0.750	1.000	1.250	1.500
0.0000	0.31988383	0.31988383	0.31988383	0.31988383	0.31988383
0.2000	0.33567370	0.33567370	0.33567370	0.33567370	0.33567370
0.4000	0.35076213	0.35076213	0.35076213	0.35076213	0.35076213
0.6000	0.36374624	0.36374624	0.36374624	0.36374624	0.36374624
0.8000	0.36200015	0.36200015	0.36200015	0.36200015	0.36200015
	MINIMUM	0.31988383	MAXIMUM	0.36374624	13.71%

08 PROFILE OF LOAD BEARING CAPACITY W.R.T. h_2/L					
$\mu^* \rightarrow h_2/L$	0.500	0.750	1.000	1.250	1.500
0.0000	0.31834943	0.31834943	0.31834943	0.31834943	0.31834943
0.2000	0.40860079	0.40860079	0.40860079	0.40860079	0.40860079
0.4000	0.47596294	0.47596294	0.47596294	0.47596294	0.47596294
0.6000	0.53252751	0.53252751	0.53252751	0.53252751	0.53252751
0.8000	0.58260178	0.58260178	0.58260178	0.58260178	0.58260178
	MINIMUM	0.31834943	MAXIMUM	0.58260178	83.01%

09 PROFILE OF LOAD BEARING CAPACITY W.R.T. m					
$\mu^* \rightarrow m$	0.500	0.750	1.000	1.250	1.500
0.0000	0.31946360	0.31946360	0.31946360	0.31946360	0.31946360
0.2000	0.33701247	0.33701247	0.33701247	0.33701247	0.33701247
0.4000	0.35168277	0.35168277	0.35168277	0.35168277	0.35168277
0.6000	0.36687132	0.36687132	0.36687132	0.36687132	0.36687132
0.8000	0.38249849	0.38249849	0.38249849	0.38249849	0.38249849
	MINIMUM	0.31946360	MAXIMUM	0.38249849	19.73%

10 PROFILE OF LOAD BEARING CAPACITY W.R.T. q					
$\mu^* \rightarrow q$	0.500	0.750	1.000	1.250	1.500
0.0000	0.47935708	0.47935708	0.47935708	0.47935708	0.47935708
0.2000	0.33501610	0.33501610	0.33501610	0.33501610	0.33501610
0.4000	0.27025087	0.27025087	0.27025087	0.27025087	0.27025087
0.6000	0.30116828	0.30116828	0.30116828	0.30116828	0.30116828
0.8000	0.97380227	0.97380227	0.97380227	0.97380227	0.97380227
	MINIMUM	0.27025087	MAXIMUM	0.97380227	260.33%

Suggestions to Enhance Understanding:

- **Mathematical Clarity:** If this explanation is part of a technical document, it would be helpful to include the specific form of Equation (15) to allow readers to verify and understand the linear dependence on the magnetization parameter.
- **Physical Implications:** Highlight any potential trade-offs or limitations of increasing magnetization, such as effects on energy consumption or operational stability, if applicable.
- **Context:** Explain where this phenomenon might be particularly advantageous in practical applications (e.g., in magnetic fluid lubrication systems).

Fruitful Conclusions:

- Studies have been made to deal with the effect of viscosity variation on the performance of a conventional lubricant based bearing system. But, literature facts to give the effect of viscosity variation on long bearing with a magnetic fluid lubricant.
- So, it was thought appropriate launch an investigation into the performance of a magnetic fluid based long bearing considering viscosity variation.
- This investigation offers the suggestion that the magnetic fluid plays a vital role in augmenting the bearing performance.
- Undoubtedly, the effect of viscosity variation fails to deliver positively for this type of bearing system always.
- It at all this type of bearing system is to be used then suitable magnetic strength must be given due priority.
- However, it is strongly felt that if designed properly, this type of bearing system may be put in use by the industry.
- This investigation beacons the researchers to extend this analysis in the following directions: Extending the analysis of this work to incorporating the roughness effect on the bearing system, as always bearing surfaces are rough to some extent (may be negligible).
- This analysis can be conducted by considering the other two magnetic fluid flow models namely: Jenkins and Shliomis.

Data Availability:

The data that has been used for this research and if so, has been mention and cited at the proper place/s.

Declaration of Competing Interest:

The authors declare that they don't have no known / unknown competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Credit Authorship Contribution Statement:

Sr. No.	Name	Description	%
1	Prin. Dr. Pragna A. Vadher	Mathematical justification	25
2	Jikisha R. Patel	Mechanical justification with problem.	25
3	Dr. Gunamani B. Deheri	Definition of problem mathematically	15
4	Pankajkumar R. Patel	Validation of the data with previous work	25
5	Rakesh M. Patel	Writing the research article	10

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